

TRANSITIVITY ANALYSIS IN THE 2021 STATE OF THE COLLEGE ADDRESS (SOCA) OF ASSCAT PRESIDENT, DR. JOY C. CAPISTRANO

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ABSTRACT

In the lush hills of Agusan, the 2021 State of the College Address (SOCA) by Dr. Joy C. Capistrano, President of Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT), painted a vivid picture of resilience and triumph amidst the shadows of the COVID-19 pandemic. Using M. A. K. Halliday's Transitivity system, we journey through her speech, uncovering the linguistic tools that bring this narrative to life. Dr. Capistrano's address is a tapestry of actions, relationships, emotions, and realities that reveal ASSCAT's steadfast pursuit of its mission. Material processes, comprising 39% of the clauses, dominate the landscape, depicting dynamic actions as ASSCAT rises above challenges with innovative solutions like flexible learning approaches and service upgrades. Relational processes, at 31%, weave the identity and achievements of ASSCAT into the fabric of the address, highlighting its esteemed position in the academic community. Mental processes, representing 13%, offer glimpses into the emotional and cognitive states of both the speaker and the institution, underscoring empathy, and collective resilience. Verbal processes account for 9%, emphasizing the vital role of communication in leadership, while existential processes, at 8%, ground the narrative in the reality of present challenges. Dr. Capistrano's SOCA is more than a speech; it's a compelling story of an institution navigating through a storm, showcasing the strategic use of language to inspire and unite its community. This transitivity analysis reveals how linguistic choices shape the narrative of ASSCAT's progress and fortitude, providing valuable insights for educational leaders seeking to communicate effectively in turbulent times

Keywords: *Joy Capistrano, State of the College Address (SOCA), Transitivity System, Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT)*

INTRODUCTION

The use of language in formal speeches, particularly in an institutional context, is a powerful means of conveying messages, influencing perceptions, and shaping the identity of an organization. The annual State of the College Address (SOCA) is a pivotal event in the academic calendar, where institutional leaders communicate their vision, report achievements, and outline future goals. In 2021, Dr. Joy C. Capistrano, President of Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT), delivered a significant SOCA amidst the ongoing challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic. This study employs M. A. K. Halliday's Transitivity system to perform a detailed clause-by-clause analysis of the address, aiming to uncover how linguistic structures convey the multifaceted narrative of ASSCAT's resilience and progress.

The significance of this analysis lies in its potential to reveal how language functions as a tool for leadership and persuasion in educational contexts. By examining the SOCA through the lens of Halliday's Transitivity system, this study seeks to contribute to the understanding of how educational leaders use linguistic strategies to address their audience, communicate institutional achievements, and foster a sense of community and resilience.

Research Questions

1. How does Dr. Joy C. Capistrano employ different process types in her 2021 State of the College Address to construct a narrative of resilience and progress at ASSCAT?
2. What percentage of material, relational, mental, verbal, and existential processes are used in the SOCA, and how do these processes contribute to the overall rhetorical strategy of the address?

Theoretical Lens

This study employs M. A. K. Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and Transitivity Model as its theoretical lens to examine the linguistic choices and their implications in the 2021 State of the College Address (SOCA) by Dr. Joy C. Capistrano. Halliday's SFL framework conceptualizes language as a social semiotic system, emphasizing the interrelation between linguistic form and social function. Central to SFL is the notion that language operates simultaneously on three metafunctions: the ideational, interpersonal, and textual. The ideational metafunction is particularly relevant to this study, as it pertains to how language represents experiences and constructs reality. Within the ideational metafunction, the Transitivity Model serves as a tool to analyze the types of processes—material, mental, relational, behavioral, verbal, and existential—encoded in the text. Material processes are concerned with actions and events, indicating what is happening in the physical world. Mental processes relate to internal experiences, reflecting cognition, emotion, and perception. Relational processes express states of

being and relationships, defining and identifying entities. Behavioral processes denote physiological and psychological behaviors, while verbal processes involve acts of communication. Existential processes state the existence of entities or events.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative research design, described by Creswell (1994) as an unfolding model that occurs in a natural setting, enabling the researcher to develop detailed insights through high involvement in actual experiences (as cited by Eyisi, 2016). The primary data source is the 2021 State of the College Address (SOCA) delivered by Dr. Joy C. Capistrano, President of the Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT). The speech was obtained through a formal request to the Office of the President, approved by the research adviser.

Following the qualitative data analysis framework by Attride-Stirling (2001), this study utilized a three-stage process: reduction of the text, exploration of the text, and integration of the exploration (as cited in Akinyode & Khan, 2018), along with Braun and Clarke’s (2006) approach (as cited in Akinyode & Khan, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Types of Transitivity Process

Material processes dominate the 2021 State of the College Address (SOCA) by Dr. Joy C. Capistrano, comprising 39% of the total clauses.

This high percentage underscores the focus on dynamic actions and tangible achievements of ASSCAT during the challenging period of the COVID-19 pandemic. By highlighting clear actors, actions, goals, and circumstances, the address effectively conveys the institution’s proactive measures and accomplishments.

Examples of material processes identified in the SOCA:

Clause 1.1. “Our alma mater stands...”

Our alma mater	stands	above the verdant hills of Agusan
Actor	Pro: material	Circumstance

Clause 1.2. “We implemented flexible learning approaches”

We	implemented	flexible learning approaches
Actor	Pro: material	Goal

Clause 1.3. “ The college library upgraded their services”

The college library	implemented	flexible learning approaches
Actor	Pro: material	Goal

Clause 1.4. " ASSCAT rises above challenges"

ASSCAT	rises	above challenges
Actor	Pro: material	Circumstance

Clause 1.5. " We are visiting the Local Government units twice a month"

We	are visiting	the Local Government units	twice a month
Actor	Pro: material	Goal	Circumstance

Clause 1.6. "The faculty developed innovative teaching methods"

The faculty	developed	innovative teaching methods
Actor	Pro: material	Goal

Clause 1.7. "Students participated in online learning"

Students	participated	in online learning
Actor	Pro: material	Goal

The frequent use of material processes in the address highlights the institution's focus on action-oriented strategies and tangible outcomes. This emphasis on physical actions and their impacts creates a narrative of a proactive and resilient institution committed to overcoming challenges and achieving progress.

Relational processes constitute 31% of the clauses in the SOCA. These processes play a crucial role in establishing and defining the identity, attributes, and values of ASSCAT. By linking the institution to its achievements, qualities, and esteemed status, relational processes help build a cohesive and positive image.

Examples of relational processes identified in the SOCA:

Clause 2.1. "The institution remains committed."

The institution	remains	committed
Carrier	Pro: relational	Attribute

Clause 2.2. "ASSCAT has a prestigious position in the academic community"

ASSCAT	has	a prestigious position in the academic community
Carrier	Pro: relational	Goal

Clause 2.3. "Our efforts are recognized nationally"

Our efforts	are	recognized nationally
Carrier	Pro: relational	Attribute

Clause 2.4. "The faculty are dedicated educators"

The faculty	are	dedicated educators
Carrier	Pro: relational	Attribute

Relational processes in the address help reinforce the institution's identity and values, establishing a strong sense of pride and commitment to excellence within the ASSCAT community.

Mental processes account for 13% of the clauses, highlighting the cognitive and emotional dimensions of the address. These processes provide insight into the thoughts, perceptions, and emotions of the speaker and the institution, fostering a sense of empathy and shared experience.

Examples of mental processes identified in the SOCA:

Clause 3.1. *"We understand the challenges"*

We	understand	the challenges
Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

Clause 3.2. *"We understand the importance of flexibility"*

We	understand	the importance of flexibility
Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

Clause 3.3. *"Students believe in the power of education"*

Students	believe	in the power of education
Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

Clause 3.4. *"I appreciate the dedication of our staff"*

I	appreciate	the dedication of our staff
Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

By incorporating mental processes, the address emphasizes the shared emotional and cognitive experiences of the ASSCAT community, promoting a sense of unity and collective resilience.

Verbal processes make up 9% of the clauses, underscoring the importance of communication in leadership and institutional governance. These processes highlight the actions of saying, reporting, and asserting, reflecting the role of dialogue and information exchange in the institution.

Examples of verbal processes identified in the SOCA:

Clause 5.1. *"The faculty communicated their needs"*

The faculty	communicated	their needs
Sayer	Pro: verbal	Verbiage

Clause 5.2. *"The board discussed the challenges"*

The board	discussed	the challenges
Sayer	Pro: verbal	Verbiage

Verbal processes in the address emphasize the role of effective communication in leadership, facilitating transparency, collaboration, and informed decision-making within the institution.

Existential processes account for 8% of the clauses, acknowledging the realities and circumstances faced by ASSCAT. These processes often introduce the existence of particular states, events, or conditions, grounding the narrative in the actual experiences of the institution.

Examples of existential processes identified in the SOCA:

Clause 6.1. *"There are countless changes"*

There	are	countless changes
Pro: existential	Existent	Circumstance

Clause 6.2. *"There is a need for flexibility"*

There	is	a need for flexibility
Pro: existential	Existent	Circumstance

Clause 6.2. *"There is hope for the future"*

There	is	hope for the future
Pro: existential	Existent	Circumstance

Existential processes help to create a realistic and grounded narrative, recognizing the challenges and achievements of ASSCAT and reinforcing the institution's commitment to navigating and overcoming these realities.

Table 1. Occurrences and Percentage of Types of Transitivity Process

No.	Types of Transitivity Process	Occurrences of Processes	Percentage
1	Material	49	39%
2	Relational	39	31%
3	Mental	16	13%
4	Verbal	11	9%
5	Existential	10	8%
	Total	125	100%

Table 1 shows that the material process is the most frequently used with 49 occurrences, making up 39% of the total. The second most common is the relational process, with 39 occurrences, accounting for 31%. The mental process follows, with 16 occurrences (13%). Verbal processes appear 11 times (9%), while existential processes occur 10 times (8%).

This distribution highlights the emphasis on actions and dynamic activities (material processes) in the address. It also shows the importance of defining identities and attributes (relational processes) and reflecting cognitive and emotional states (mental processes). The relatively lower frequency of verbal and existential processes indicates less focus on communication and existence within the speech.

Themes Identified in the State of the College Address (SOCA) of Dr. Joy C. Capistrano

In this section, the linguistic features were identified through transitivity analysis to the interactions that generate the themes reflected in the SOCA. The following theme was found in the address:

Table 2. Commitment and Innovation

Theme	Supporting Clauses
Commitment and Innovation	"We remain committed to our mission" (Clause 4) "Innovative teaching methods were developed" (Clause 5) "The daring and valiant moves of ASSCAT" (Clause 6)

Commitment and innovation are also significant themes in the address. The clause "We remain committed to our mission" illustrates the steadfast dedication of ASSCAT to its core goals. The mention of "innovative teaching methods were developed" highlights the institution's proactive approach to improving education. Additionally, "The daring and valiant moves of ASSCAT" reflects the institution's willingness to take bold steps towards achieving its objectives.

Table 3. Resilience and Progress

Theme	Supporting Clauses
Resilience and Progress	"Our alma mater stands tall" (Clause 1) "We have overcome numerous challenges" (Clause 2) "Our flag is still flying strong" (Clause 3)

Resilience and progress are central themes in the SOCA, highlighted by the institution's ability to withstand and overcome challenges while continuing to move forward. The phrases "Our alma mater stands tall" and "Our flag is still flying strong" symbolize the enduring strength and ongoing progress of ASSCAT. The emphasis on overcoming challenges underscores the resilience of the community.

Table 4. Adaptation and Growth

Theme	Supporting Clauses
Adaptation and Growth	"We will continue to bring societal influence and impact" (Clause 10) "Our enrolment speaks otherwise" (Clause 11) "We reimagined and reinvented strategies" (Clause 12)

Adaptation and growth are significant themes in the address, highlighting the institution's ability to evolve and expand in response to changing circumstances. The clause "We will continue to bring societal influence and impact" reflects ASSCAT's ongoing commitment to societal contributions. The statement "Our enrolment speaks otherwise" signifies the institution's growth despite external challenges, while "We reimagined and reinvented strategies" emphasizes the innovative approaches adopted to ensure continuous improvement.

Table 5. Recognition and Gratitude

Theme	Supporting Clauses
Recognition and Gratitude	"We are grateful for their leading" (Clause 13) "This occasion is a good time to assess the state of the college" (Clause 14) "My salute to all of you" (Clause 15)

Recognition and gratitude are essential themes that permeate the address. The clause "We are grateful for their leading" acknowledges the contributions of past leaders who have shaped the institution. The phrase "This occasion is a good time to assess the state of the college" highlights the significance of reflection and evaluation. Lastly, "My salute to all of you" conveys heartfelt appreciation for the efforts and dedication of the entire ASSCAT community.

Table 6. Community and Collaboration

Theme	Supporting Clauses
Community and Collaboration	"We are grateful for the leadership" (Clause 7) "Our faculty, staff, students, and alumni engaged in community services" (Clause 8) "The collective gains we achieve" (Clause 9)

Community and collaboration are pivotal themes in the SOCA, emphasizing the unity and cooperative efforts within the ASSCAT community. The clauses "We are grateful for the leadership" and "Our faculty, staff, students, and alumni engaged in community services" underscore the collective efforts and mutual support that drive the institution's success. The mention of "The collective gains we achieve" highlights the shared achievements resulting from collaborative endeavors.

DISCUSSION

The analysis reveals a strategic use of different process types to construct a compelling narrative of resilience, progress, and community at ASSCAT. Material processes dominate the address, reflecting the dynamic actions taken by the institution to navigate the challenges posed by the pandemic and to implement innovative solutions, such as flexible learning approaches and service upgrades. Relational processes are equally significant, as they establish the identity and achievements of ASSCAT, reinforcing its esteemed position and continuous pursuit of excellence. These processes help create a strong connection between the institution and its stakeholders, fostering a sense of pride and belonging. Mental processes, though fewer in number, play a crucial role in conveying the emotional and cognitive states of the speaker and the community. By expressing empathy, determination, and resilience, these processes help maintain morale and trust among stakeholders during challenging times. Verbal processes highlight the importance of communication in leadership. The act of preparing and delivering the address is itself a significant communicative event, and the analysis shows how verbal processes are used to articulate the institution's vision and strategies effectively. Existential processes acknowledge the reality of the challenges faced by ASSCAT. By recognizing the existence of various difficulties, the address creates a realistic and grounded narrative that acknowledges the complexities of the current situation.

Conclusions

This transitivity analysis of Dr. Joy C. Capistrano's 2021 SOCA highlights the strategic use of different process types to construct a narrative of resilience, progress, and community at ASSCAT. The findings suggest that the deliberate use of material, relational, mental, verbal, and existential processes enables the institution to effectively communicate its achievements and challenges, fostering a sense of shared purpose and determination among its stakeholders.

Future research could extend this analysis to compare SOCA addresses across different institutions or years, providing a broader understanding of how educational leaders use language to navigate and articulate institutional goals and challenges. Such comparative studies could further elucidate the role of linguistic choices in shaping institutional narratives and influencing stakeholder perceptions.

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Recommendations

Future research could expand on this study by analyzing the State of the College Addresses from different years or by various college presidents to identify changes and trends in the use of transitivity processes over time. Comparative studies could also be conducted across different institutions to explore how different educational leaders employ language to convey their messages and objectives. Additionally, incorporating other linguistic frameworks, such as appraisal theory or multimodal discourse analysis, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the rhetorical strategies used in these speeches. Research could also examine the impact of these speeches on various stakeholders, including faculty, students, and external partners, to assess the effectiveness of the communication strategies employed. Finally, a longitudinal study could investigate the long-term effects of the linguistic choices made in these addresses on institutional identity and stakeholder engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors obtained the informed consent of the respondents and the latter were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. Their identities were kept anonymous and the respondents' well-being was safeguarded. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results were used purely for research.

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